

Additional data

This document presents the reported results for all participants (8) of our experiment on all tasks (8).

Results from Participants 10.06 and 10.02 are presented but were not taken into account due to unexpected recording issues discovered after analysis (see the Method section in the paper). Their figures are presented after the other participants.

Tasks 97, 103 and 109 (resp. b_6, b_9 and b_11) were ranked as *most difficult* by participants. Other tasks were seen as easier, especially 79, 67 and 85 (resp. b_1, a_1 and b_2), considered as *easiest*.

Easiest tasks do not expose clusters of fixations. Since we define critical PoC based on clusters of fixations with long duration, the alignment in those tasks is hard to investigate.

The 8 first figures are the aggregated results of all participants for each task.

Note: for a better readability please refer to the figures in the attached folder.

Aggregated results

Figure 1 SID 97 - task b_6

Figure 2 SID 109 - task b_11

Figure 3 SID 103 - task b_9

Figure 4 SID 73 - task a_2

Figure 5 SID 91 - task b_3

Easiest tasks

Figure 6 SID 85 - task b_2

Figure 7 SID 67 - task a_1

Figure 8 SID 79 - task b_1

Individual results

Figures are presented by task and then by order of participants' unique id (UID):

10.05 – 10.09 – 10.04 – 10.03 – 10.07 – 10.01 – 10.06 – 10.02

As mentioned, the last two participants presented recording issues.

SID 97 – task b_6

SID 109 – task b_11

SID 103 – task b_9

SID 91 – task b_3

SID 85 – task b_2

SID 67 – task a_1

SID 79 – task b_1

